

Ecuador's electricity crisis: misinformation aggravates uncertainty

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Ineffective communication of the electricity crisis in Ecuador is generating conflict. Opinion leaders demand continuity and timeliness in the information presented by the ministry and the committee in charge of dealing with this catastrophe.

It is not the first time this year, let alone in the last decade, that citizens have had to change their routines as a result of power cuts. But each time the public bulletins are contradictory and have inaccuracies that lead to disinformation, i.e. news constructed with the intention to confuse or to benefit the issuers of the hoaxes.

In the face of uncertainty, economic losses and the suspension of classes, among other consequences, it is necessary, in addition to constant communication processes, to teach people how to live efficiently using natural resources. This need is highlighted by international organizations, scientific institutions and environmental protection associations that warn of the droughts, fires, and floods caused by climate change.

There are advertisements to encourage people to turn off unused lights, or the correct way to take a shower, but there are also buildings with lights on after hours and industries that do not treat wastewater, not to mention rivers full of quicksilver from mining.

It is therefore urgent to communicate what, how and where to mitigate the effects of water scarcity and abundance in the coming months and years. Recommendations to prevent the misuse of environmental assets, which have been written down, must be put into practice, but without political will they will remain as a prosecution argument to judge those responsible for ecological crimes.